

"No Wall is Thick Enough to Stop Them" - Transmediality and Colonial-Critical Resistance in French West Africa 1900 – 1914

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Between 1900 and 1914, brochures, lithographs, and newspapers printed in Bologna, Cairo, New York, and Hamburg circulated freely in French West Africa, largely beyond the control of colonial authorities. This paper examines how these cross-media and cross-border connections significantly influenced the rise of a colonial-critical consciousness in the region through an interplay between local and global forces. The paper advocates for a critical reassessment of the concept of mass media, emphasizing the importance of transmedia competences and the practices they enable. It further argues that individuals occupying cultural intermediary roles within imperial contexts often possessed greater media competence than colonial rulers, a skillset that could be strategically applied in anti-colonial struggle.

1. The Sultan's Portrait

In August 1911, French colonial authorities intercepted a shipment of one hundred postal packages at the port of Dakar, Senegal (ANS 19G4). Each package contained high-quality art prints from a small printing press in Bologna, addressed to a Dakar-based Moroccan merchant. While the images themselves were not explicitly anti-colonial, the French authorities were highly alerted. A significant portion of the cargo consisted of portraits of the Sultan of Egypt (see figure 1), which the French interpreted as part of a pan-Islamic propaganda campaign aimed at undermining their influence in West Africa. This suspicion was seemingly confirmed by the sender of the prints: Abdel Hamed Zaki, an anti-colonial Egyptian activist, living in Bologna, where he published an anti-colonial caricature magazine notorious for its sharp criticism of European imperialism, the *Cairo Punch* (Booth 2013; Byron 2019)

Figure 1: *Sultans et Princes d'Islam, Cairo Punch 1911, Archives Nationales du Benin*

The confiscation of the Cairo Punch in the summer of 1911 is the micro-historical vantage point for this paper. In what follows, I will advance two arguments that bring together global transmedia history (Asseraf 2022; Cronqvist; Hilgert 2017) and new trans-imperial history (Brückenhausen 2017; Goebel 2016; Marsh 2019). First, I argue that global transmedia history provides a lens through which the inherent fragility of imperial rule and the lack of colonial control over information can be observed. The circulation of Cairo Punch prints exemplifies how a West African public sphere was able to form independent connections with other empire-critical publics in the Global South, illustrating an imperial loss of control. As one official remarked on the circulation of empire-critical information: 'No wall is thick enough to stop them' (ANS 21G24 versemment 108).

Secondly, as a media impact study, this paper posits that transregional entanglements significantly influenced cultural and political dynamics at the local level. This influence can be observed in how individuals, drawing on an enhanced transmedia competence due to their social and cultural position, engaged in self-politicization through the interplay of written, oral and visual carriers of information. The incorporation of Cairo Punch prints into local contexts by West-African middle-class actors catalysed the rise of one of Africa's first democratic, anti-colonial movements, the Jeunes Sénégalais (1913 – 1920).

2. Transmedia Densification and Colonial Fragility in French West Africa 1900 – 1914

Founded in 1907, the Cairo Punch was a sophisticated medium. Its editor, Abdel Hamid Zaki printed cartoons and illustrations in Bologna and sent them to Cairo, where they were put together with trilingual texts (Arabic, English and French). After the interception of the cargo in Dakar, the French authorities feared that someone in Senegal might assemble the images with anti-imperial text modules in a similar manner (ANS 19G4). However, it rather appeared that Zaki tailored his prints to local needs and demand. Nevertheless, the import of his prints disrupted an imperial media regime, which relied on a hierarchical diffusion of information from the metropolis to the periphery. Unsurprisingly, the French viewed this loss of control as a threat to their authority.

This colonial fragility is best illustrated through the link between the circulation of the Cairo Punch and the development of a distinct Senegalese technique of reversed glass painting: Suwer (*sous-verre*). While studies have examined Suwers from the 1950s to the 1980s, the origins of this technique remain obscure (Baj-Strobel 2013; Bouttiaux 1994). Recently, art historian Giulia Paoletti has linked Suwers to the global spread of portrait photography and depictions of saints from the Middle East, which reached Senegal in the late 19th century (Paoletti 2018; 2024, 62 – 68). Building on her ideas and my own archival research in Benin and Senegal, I contest earlier research that posits that Suwer originated as a response to colonial censorship by replicating banned art prints to meet local demand (Baj-Strobel 2013, 244). This assumption rests on the notion of effective colonial censorship, which archival evidence contradicts.

Archival records reveal thirty-three confiscations of lithographs, chromolithographs, brochures, and other imported media across West Africa between 1911 and 1916 (ANS 19G1-6; ANB 4E15). These discoveries often happened by chance. In December 1914, for instance, French authorities in Conakry seized a German shipment of over 850 chromolithographs, mainly portraits of Arab royals and leaders of Egyptian and Turkish Young-movements. Apparently, only heightened scrutiny of German cargo during World War I brought the shipment to attention (ANS 19G4).

The various imported media should be regarded as parts of a single, cohesive media flow that countered the European imperial portrayal of Islam. While French propaganda around 1900 depicted Islam as fanatical and resistant to progress (Harrison 1990, 29), publications like Cairo Punch and Egyptian newspapers presented a modern, dignified, and powerful Muslim world, often organised around portraits of Muslim royals. These portraits were integrated into local visual regimes, including Suwers. Findings from private collections suggest that portraits of sultans were a prominent motif in early Suwers. These generic portraits appeared as standalone motifs or as additions to religious images, serving as carriers of political information (Paoletti 2018; Samuel 2014, 2017, 2019; Schulz 2014). Rather than being a reaction to colonial censorship, Suwers supplemented the circulation of

images and texts from Beirut, Cairo, Bologna, and Hamburg, reflecting a cross-media densification of a globally entangled, local public sphere.

This densification can be further understood by considering the oral dimensions of a Senegalese public. Michelle Baj-Stobel has noted that reverse glass painting in Senegal was closely tied to oral knowledge transfer (Baj-Stobel 2013, 245-246) In Senegal, oral traditions were institutionalized by griots, oral historians who chronicled the reigns of Senegalese aristocrats. By the late 19th and early 20th centuries, the role of griots evolved alongside a globally interconnected Senegalese society. They became advertising agents for local traders, political mobilizers, and entertainers for the urban bourgeoisie (Diop 1935). This Senegalese bourgeoisie (Dejung; Motadel; Osterhammel 2019), the primary consumer of Cairo Punch prints, Suwers, and Arabic newspapers, occupied a unique intercultural position. Often trained in Islamic and French-schools, they combined the ability to read texts in both languages, with the financial means to afford luxury items like art prints and Suwers.

For this urban upper strata of Senegalese society, portraits of Muslim royals not only fostered a sense of affiliation with the Muslim world but served as repositories of local oral traditions. Griots, or other institutions engaging in oral knowledge transmission, might incorporate these portraits into their practices, linking visual and oral communication. As one French report suggests, teachers at Islamic schools used images from the Cairo Punch as educational tools (ANS 19G4). In Saint-Louis du Sénégal, the library of a wealthy merchant, serving as a gathering place for the local intelligentsia, featured a family tree of the Egyptian royals, complete with portraits (ANS 10D0069; Diop 2003, 159). In this social context, these images acted as a media bridge between orality and visuality, intertwining global and local references.

3. The Jeunes Sénégalais : Bridging ‘Global Waves’ and Local Contexts

These “cross-border and cross-medial overlappings” (Cronqvist; Hilgert 2017, 131) produced concrete political outcomes. It allowed for a Senegalese urban intelligentsia to situate their local political concerns into a global discourse while simultaneously adapting global political narratives to address local issues.

In 1913, a group of Senegalese intellectuals founded one of the first anti-colonial movements on the African continent in the city of Saint-Louis, the Jeunes Sénégalais (Gueye 1964, 18 – 20; ANS 20G21) Prior to the First World War, the group advocated for substantial reforms within the French Empire, including the extension of citizenship to West African populations. The similarity between their name and those of contemporary movements in Egypt or Turkey was no coincidence but the result of discursive entanglements that enabled the movement to align itself with a “global constitutional wave.” (Sohrabi 2002, 45)

In their efforts to prevent the entanglement of a West African public sphere, the colonial authorities inadvertently contributed to the rise of the Jeunes Sénégalais. As early as 1911, when issues of Cairo Punch were confiscated, the French authorities recognized that their ability to enforce censorship was undermined by a lack of translators (ANS 19G4). Consequently, all intercepted media was sent to Saint-Louis to be translated and checked for content, as the city was home the sole institutions in French West Africa dedicated to training local Arabic translators (ANS J93). With these translators drawn from the politicized West-African urban upper classes, the colonial administration inundated the already most politically subversive point of its system with newspapers, pamphlets, and images discussing Arab reform movements. One of these translators subscribed to a banned Young Egyptian newspaper in 1910 (ANS 19G4), while another translator working there in 1912 was a co-founder of the Jeunes Sénégalais (Gueye 1964, 18 – 20).

In conclusion, the circulation and mutual stimulation of different media with shared Empire-critical themes shows that a West African public successfully connected with other publics in the global South, circumventing colonial control. Shifting from media distribution to an analysis of media impact, it becomes clear that these transregional entanglements had significant cultural and political effects within the “small spaces” (Adelman; Bell; Motadel; Drayton 2018) of Senegalese cities. On the one hand, it influenced the technique of Senegalese reverse glass painting, establishing it as a

distinct media tradition. On the other hand, cross-media densification within the Senegalese bourgeoisie, equipped with the social and cultural capital to integrate diverse media into a unified political outlook, played a key role in the emergence of one of the continent's earliest colonial-critical movements.

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